

Notes on the MEDem ATLAS Prototype

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ABSTRACT:

This short note introduces the MEDem ATLAS prototype: an online application designed to demonstrate the potential of concept-driven dataset annotation for facilitating comparative social science research. The system implements a structured data model linking an ontology of theoretical concepts to tabular datasets containing variables and metadata. Within this framework, concepts for object properties—such as attributes of persons or political parties—are defined and organized hierarchically into dimensions, subdimensions, and indicator concepts, each supported by literature-based definitions. These conceptual elements are systematically connected to empirical operationalizations through a variables database that records how indicators are measured across datasets. By linking conceptual knowledge to dataset metadata, the tool enables interactive exploration of conceptual coverage across datasets and facilitates the identification and comparison of available operationalizations. The system also includes a Research Builder tool that allows users to select concepts relevant to a research question and automatically identify datasets containing corresponding indicators, while providing detailed information on measurement coverage. The prototype further demonstrates the possibility for cross-dataset linkage and generates automated scripts for preliminary analysis in common data science languages. Overall, MEDem ATLAS illustrates how ontology-based annotation can enhance transparency, comparability, and efficiency in secondary data analysis.

The MEDem ATLAS prototype is an online application demonstrating some of the potential of dataset annotation following the data model and procedures presented in De Sio, Katsanidou and Borghetto (under review on PS: Political Science and Politics).

Its internal data structure consists of:

- 1) An ontology document system storing, for each top-level object property concept,
 - a) a brief definition with literature references.
 - b) details about its articulation into subdimensions, and finally into indicator concepts.
- 2) Tabular Datasets: This consists of two interconnected tables:
 - a) A "datasets" table, with one row for each dataset.
 - b) A "variables" table, containing one row for every variable within each dataset. This table also incorporates entity references for variables whose values represent real-world entities.

The combination and linking of this information enables the automated, interactive generation of meaningful views (beyond the scope of harmonization tasks), as exemplified below.

The initial Concepts view (Figure 1) outlines conceptualizations by coding the properties of various objects (such as Persons and Political Parties). These conceptualizations are further structured by their division into dimensions and corresponding indicators.

Figure 1 – The initial Concepts view

Figure 2 shows an example (mock-up) entry for religiosity (a property Concept entry: Religiosity is a property of a Person). Note the implementation of concepts-variables linkage: within each Subdimension, each Indicator concept links to actual operationalizations – “measures” – available in different datasets.

Figure 2 – A (property) Concept entry

A drill-down view (see Figure 3) shows the potential of this concept-centric scheme to easily organize operationalizations across multiple languages.

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL localhost:3000/medem/concepts/dbo:P... The page displays a concept hierarchy for 'Nonorganizational: Attitudes' with sub-items like 'Belief In God', 'Prayer', and 'How Religious'. A modal window titled 'Measures of How Religious from the Variables database:' is open, showing a table of operationalizations for three languages: German, Czech, and Danish.

Dataset	Variable	Label	Language	Introduction text	Question text	Values and labels	
SQP Tests for: ESS Round 1 - Austria	RlgDgr	RlgDgr	German	.	Ungeachtet der Tatsache, ob Sie einer bestimmten Religion angehören, für wie religiös halten Sie sich? Bitte verwenden Sie diese Karte für Ihre Antwort.	0	Überhaupt nicht religiös
						1	
						2	
						3	
						4	
						5	
						6	
						7	translate
						8	
						9	
10	Sehr						
	translate						
SQP Tests for: ESS Round 1 - Czech Republic	RlgDgr	RlgDgr	Czech	.	Jak jste zbožný - bez ohledu na to, zda se hlásíte k nějakému konkrétnímu náboženství?	00	Vůbec nejsem zbožný
						01	
						02	
						03	
						04	translate
						05	
						06	
						07	
						08	
						09	
10	Jsem velmi zbožný						
	translate						
SQP Tests for: ESS Round 1 - Denmark	RlgDgr	RlgDgr	Danish	.	Uanset om du tilhører en bestemt religion eller ej, hvor religiøs vil du sige, at du er? På en skala fra 0 til 10, hvor 0 betyder slet ikke religiøs og 10 betyder meget religiøs.	00	Slet ikke religiøs
						01	
						02	
						03	
						04	
						05	
						06	
						07	translate
08							

Figure 3 – Drill-down view of Indicator-linked operationalizations from different datasets

The Data view (Figure 4) shows a first important potential of the linkage between the Concepts knowledge graph and the Variables database. Due to this architecture, it's easy to implement, in the Data view, the ability to quickly review the conceptual coverage available in different datasets.

Figure 4 – The initial Data view

But perhaps this potential is made available in an even more productive fashion in the Research Builder (Figure 5). This tool makes very easy to quickly find datasets including at least one indicator for each of several concepts that are relevant for a research question.

Figure 5 – The Research Builder starting page

In the second step in the Research Builder (Figure 6), Subdimension and Indicator coverage is shown for each dataset (showing the relevant variables), for all the concepts selected in the previous step. This makes easy for the researcher to identify, among candidate datasets, which offers the conceptual coverage that best suits her research needs, along with actual operationalization details.

As a result, for a set of concepts relevant for a research question, detailed information about breadth and quality of measurement coverage of each concept can be reviewed and compared across multiple datasets.

Importantly, in this step the researcher can also select options for cross-dataset linkage. In the example shown in Figure 6, a number of different party-related variables from the EES 2009 Voter study (the “main” dataset) can be used as linkage keys towards other datasets about political parties (here, CHES 1999-2019 and EES 2009 Euromanifesto appear available for linkage).

The screenshot displays the 'Dataset selection' interface of the MEDEM ATLAS system. The browser address bar shows 'localhost:3000/medem/secondary1/dbo:Person/Party%20Identification%20[7].Voti...'. The page header includes the MEDEM ATLAS logo and navigation links for Objects, Concepts, Data, and Tools. The main content area is titled 'Dataset selection' and contains a search bar and a table of datasets. The table has columns for Dataset, Available external links, Party Identification, Voting Behavior, Issue Positions, and Media Use. The first dataset listed is 'European Parliament Election Study 2009, Voter Study' with a 'Select' button. The table lists various indicators and their descriptions across different datasets.

Dataset	Available external links	Party Identification	Voting Behavior	Issue Positions	Media Use
European Parliament Election Study 2009, Voter Study dbo:Person	q25 (q25 Which party voted for in EP elections) <input type="checkbox"/> dbo:PoliticalParty:	<i>Direction</i> Which Party Feel Closer To: q87 (q87 close to a party [pid])	<i>Party Vote</i> Party Voted For In Last National Election: q27 (q27 Actual vote in last general election)	<i>Civil Rights</i> Homosexuals Should Be Free To Be With Whom They Want: q58 (q58 agree/disagree: Same-sex marriages should be prohibited by law)	<i>Internet Use</i> Use Of Internet: Use Of Internet On Politics: q20 (q20 how often look into website concerned with election?)
CHES1999-2019	<input type="checkbox"/> dbo:PoliticalParty:	q89 (q89 not close to a party - but closer to a party?)	Party Voted For In Last Eu Election: q25 (q25 Which party voted for in EP elections)	Stance On Abortion: q60 (q60 agree/disagree: Women should be free to decide on matters of abortion)	Newspaper Use Total Use Of Newspaper: q13 (q13 Read other paper more frequently?)
EES2009Euromanifesto	q26 (q26 Which party, if R had voted in EP elections) <input type="checkbox"/> dbo:PoliticalParty:	<i>Intensity</i> How Close To Each Political Party: q88 (q88 close or sympathizer)	Turnout Voted: Voted In The Eu Election: q24 (q24 Did or did not vote in EP elections)	<i>Economy</i> Stance On Income Equality: q63 (q63 agree/disagree: Income and wealth should be redistributed towards ordinary people)	q15a (q15a days a week read other paper 1st)
CHES1999-2019	<input type="checkbox"/> dbo:PoliticalParty:		Vote Intention First Vote Preference: q28 (q28 Vote intention in general elections)	Fair Level Of Gross Pay: Stance On Government Intervention Economy: q57 (q57 agree/disagree: Private enterprise best to solve [country's] economic problems)	q15b (q15b days a week read other paper 2nd)
EES2009Euromanifesto	q28 (q28 Vote intention in general elections) <input type="checkbox"/> dbo:PoliticalParty:		Second Vote Preference: q59 (q59 agree/disagree: public services and industries should be in state ownership)	Stance On Private Enterprise Best Solution: Stance On State Ownership:	q15c (q15c days a week read other paper 3rd)
CHES1999-2019	<input type="checkbox"/> dbo:PoliticalParty:			Immigration Evaluation Of Allowing Immigrants From Poorer Non-european Countries: Evaluation Of Allowing Immigrants Of Different Race:	q15d (q15d days a week read other paper 4th)
EES2009Euromanifesto	q90 (q90 not close but closer to party- which?) <input type="checkbox"/> dbo:PoliticalParty:				q15e (q15e days a week read other paper 5th)

Figure 6 – The Research Builder dataset selection step

Finally, the Research Builder, currently in its pilot phase, will provide the researcher with an automatically generated kick-start script in the most common data science languages, such as Stata, R, and Python. The script will include:

- information on how to obtain the dataset(s) from the appropriate archives;
- automatically-generated syntax performing linkage among the selected datasets (if selected: not shown in the example);
- automatically-generated syntax for descriptive analyses of all variables linked to the originally selected concepts, along with extensive comments detailing the role of the variable in the concept articulation, and actual operationalization information (e.g., question wording for survey data).

This kick-start script, with its inclusion of conceptual and operationalization information, is deliberately designed to encourage concept- and measurement-aware data analysis.